

MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES WITH ULTRA-THIN PLYS FOR CRYOGENIC ENVIRONMENTS: MECHANICAL TESTING AND PERMEABILITY

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Baltimore (Maryland), August 6th, 2025

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Liquid Hydrogen
(LH₂)
70g/L at 20K and 4 bar

60g/L at 150K and 700 bar

40g/L at 150K and 350 bar

Cryo-compressed
Hydrogen
(CcH₂)

Y. Yan, J. Zhang, G. Li, W. Zhou, and Z. Ni, "Review on linerless type V cryo-compressed hydrogen storage vessels: Resin toughening and hydrogen-barrier properties control," Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, vol. 189, p. 114009, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2023.114009.

Liquid H₂ tank

<https://h2businessnews.com/airbus-desarrolla-tanques-criogenicos-para-los-vuelos-propulsados-por-hidrogeno/>

AIRBUS

<https://actualidad aeroespacial.com/airbus-esta-desarrollando-innovadores-tanques-criogenicos-para-los-vuelos-propulsados-por-hidrogeno/>

CFRP for LH₂ type-V tank

**LH₂ storage conditions:
1-7 bar and -253°C**

The use of UTP plies in combination with conventional plies may inhibit or modify the generation of certain phases of the damage mechanism in CFRP composite laminates ⁽¹⁾

The use of composite films (graphene nano-platelets, carbon nano-fibres, carbon nano-tubes...) could act as H₂ barriers versus leakage ^(2,3)

Could UTPs improve the mechanical behaviour of CFRP LH₂ tanks?

STAGE 1

Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures:

- Thermo-mechanical material characterisation at cryogenic temperatures
- State of the material microstructure after cryogenic exposure

EXPERIMENTAL

STAGE 2

Role of UTPs in quasi-isotropic laminates under LH₂ tank conditions:

- Stress and damage distribution considering biaxial loading and/or cryogenic exposure
- Leakage testing of laminates after thermo-mechanical testing

EXPERIMENTAL
ANALYTICAL/NUMERICAL

(1) Sánchez-Carmona, S., Correa, E., Barroso, A., & París, F. (2023). Experimental observations of fatigue damage in cross-ply laminates using carbon/epoxy ultra-thin plies. *Composite Structures*, 306 (116564).

(2) Zotti, A., Zuppolini, S., Borriello, A., Vinti, V., Trinchillo, L., & Zarrelli, M. (2024). The Effect of Carbon-Based Nanofillers on Cryogenic Temperature Mechanical Properties of CFRPs. *Polymers* 2024, Vol. 16, Page 638, 16(5), 638.

(3) Yan, Y., Zhang, J., Li, G., Zhou, W., & Ni, Z. (2024). Review on linerless type V cryo-compressed hydrogen storage vessels: Resin toughening and hydrogen-barrier properties control. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 189, 114009.

➤ STAGE 1:

- Experimental material characterisation at room temperature (RT) after cryogenic exposure:
 - 1) under (tensile and shear) mechanical loading
 - 2) under thermal loading
- Comparison of the material characterisation with the material as manufactured (AM) (previously characterized by the authors⁽¹⁾)
- Understanding the material microstructure after cryogenic exposure

➤ STAGE 2:

- Determination of biaxial testing conditions at room temperature that best reproduce the real conditions of a QI CFRP laminate in a LH2 tank with the available infrastructure

REAL CONDITIONS:

Curved panels (tank) subjected to internal pressure (biaxial stress state) + cryogenic temperature

LAB CONDITIONS:

Biaxial testing of flat panels at RT

(1) Sánchez-Carmona S. et al., Thermomechanical characterisation data of 30 g/m² and 150 g/m² cured unidirectional carbon/epoxy tape prepreg TP 402/T700S. *Data in Brief*, 47, 0–7 (2023)

What can be found in literature regarding composites characterization under cryogenics?

➤ General aspects regarding some properties:

- ❑ studying the resin independently ⁽¹⁻³⁾
- ❑ modifying the resin formulation ⁽⁴⁾
- ❑ without expounding a complete characterisation for a specific composite material ⁽⁵⁾

➤ Some material behaviours seem to improve tested under cryogenics ⁽⁶⁾

➤ Material properties seem not to be prominently altered by thermal cycling ⁽⁷⁻⁸⁾

➤ Very few studies analyse long-term exposures at cryogenics ⁽⁹⁾

- (1) Ueki, T., Nishijima, S., & Izumi, Y. (2005). Designing of epoxy resin systems for cryogenic use. *Cryogenics*, 45(2), 141–148.
- (2) Mishra, K., & Singh, R. P. (2013). Reinforcement of epoxy resins with POSS for enhancing fracture toughness at cryogenic temperature. *Conference Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Mechanics Series*, 7, 179–187.
- (3) Li, H., Chen, G., Su, H., Li, D., Sun, L., & Yang, J. (2019). Effect of the stoichiometric ratio on the crosslinked network structure and cryogenic properties of epoxy resins cured at low temperature. *European Polymer Journal*, 112, 792–798.
- (4) Kim, M. G., Kang, S. G., Kim, C. G., & Kong, C. W. (2010). Tensile properties of carbon fiber composites with different resin compositions at cryogenic temperatures. *Advanced Composite Materials*, 19(1), 63–77.
- (5) Sethi, S., & Ray, B. C. (2013). Mechanical behavior of polymer composites at cryogenic temperatures. In *Polymers at Cryogenic Temperatures* (Vol. 9783642353352, pp. 59–113). Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- (6) Sun, W., Wu, Z., Huang, C., Wang, Z., Huang, R., Gong, L., Nishimura, A., Zhou, Y., & Li, L. (2023). Investigation on cryogenic mechanical properties of basalt fiber-reinforced epoxy composites. *Cryogenics*, 132, 103684.
- (7) Lüders, C., & Sinapius, M. (2019). Fatigue of fibre-reinforced plastics due to cryogenic thermal cycling. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 53(20), 2849–2861.
- (8) Chen, W., Wang, Y., Zhang, K., & Xu, F. (2021). Characterization and comparison of properties of cryogenic conditioned CNT reinforced thermoset (epoxy) and thermoplastic (poly vinyl alcohol) composite yarns. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 55(30), 4503–4511.
- (9) Nikonovich, M., Ramalho, A., & Emami, N. (2024). Effect of cryogenic aging and test-environment on the tribological and mechanical properties of PEEK composites. *Tribology International*, 194, 109554.

STAGE 1 Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures

- Thermo-mechanical material characterisation at cryogenic temperatures
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➤ Material characterisation at RT

- Mechanical (E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , G_{12} , X_T , Y_T , S)
- Thermal (α_1 , α_2)

after cryogenic exposure in LN2 immersion (77K):

- a) 24h
- b) 144h

MATERIAL

Prepreg carbono/epoxy

TP402/T700S

Thermocouples embedded in reference samples

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Stiffness (E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , G_{12})

(1) Sánchez-Carmona S. et al., Thermomechanical characterisation data of 30 g/m² and 150 g/m² cured unidirectional carbon/epoxy tape prepreg TP 402/T700S. *Data in Brief*, 47, 0–7 (2023)

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Strength (X_T , Y_T , S)

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CTE (α_1, α_2)

(1) Sánchez-Carmona S. et al., Thermomechanical characterisation data of 30 g/m² and 150 g/m² cured unidirectional carbon/epoxy tape prepreg TP 402/T700S. *Data in Brief*, 47, 0–7 (2023)

Measured in an oven for the range temperature [333,363] K

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MATRIX STATE (AM)

STAGE 1 Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures

- Thermo-mechanical material characterisation at cryogenic temperatures
- State of the material microstructure after cryogenic exposure

MATRIX STATE (After 144h in LN2)

STAGE 1 Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures

- Thermo-mechanical material characterisation at cryogenic temperatures
- State of the material microstructure after cryogenic exposure

FIBRE STATE

AM

After LN2 exposure for 144h

STAGE 1 Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures

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➤ **Proposal of quasi-isotropic (QI) laminates for LH2 storage tank to reduce leakages:**

▪ $[45/90/-45/0]_{2s}$

- CN laminate: 150 g/m² prepreg.
- CN+UT laminate: as CN, except that the 0° and 90° plies are made of 50 g/m² prepreg.
- CN-UT-CN consists of external blocks made using 150 g/m² prepreg and internal blocks made using 50 g/m² prepreg.

STAGE 2

Role of UTPs in quasi-isotropic laminates under LH2 tank conditions:

- Stress and damage distribution considering biaxial loading and/or cryogenic exposure
- Leakage testing of laminates after thermo-mechanical testing

	E ₁₁ (MPa)	E ₂₂ (MPa)	E ₃₃ (MPa)	ν ₁₂	ν ₁₃	ν ₂₃	G ₁₂ (MPa)	Y _T (MPa)	X _T (MPa)	S (MPa)	α ₁ (°C ⁻¹)	α ₂ (°C ⁻¹)	α ₃ (°C ⁻¹)
ORIGINAL P.	113910	7810	7810	0,321	0,321	0,4	3254	38	2040	65	6,16E-06	2,95E-05	3,03E-05
MODIFIED P.	101722	8150	8150	0,26	0,264	0,4	3082	31	2026	62	4,50E-06	3,88E-05	3,99E-05

➤ Prediction of the stress state of QI curved laminates in 'real' conditions in the LH2 body tank:

- ✓ Cryogenic temperature
- ✓ Thermo-mechanical properties (from the previous tests)
- ✓ Internal pressure

Analytical/MEF model of QI curved panels

Analytical/MEF model of QI flat panels

Experimental biaxial tests on QI flat specimens

Due to the complexity of the actual damage mechanisms in composites (UTPs) the accurate determination of K ratio for the cases to be experimentally tested seems relevant

STAGE 2 Role of UTPs in quasi-isotropic laminates under LH2 tank conditions:

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BIAXIAL TESTING FOR QI LAMINATES

CURVED LAMINATE

Ansys

Analytical		Conv.	Conv.	0/90 UTP	0/90 UTP
		(O.P.)	(M.P.)	(O.P.)	(M.P.)
0°	σ_{11} (MPa)	203	170	-75	-94
	σ_{22} (MPa)	147	192	207	262
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
90°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1090	1043	2046	1979
	σ_{22} (MPa)	101	140	106	137
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
45°	σ_{11} (MPa)	647	607	986	943
	σ_{22} (MPa)	126	166	156	199
	σ_{12} (MPa)	26	27	62	64

FEM		Conv.	Conv.	0/90 UTP	0/90 UTP
		(O.P.)	(M.P.)	(O.P.)	(M.P.)
0°	σ_{11} (MPa)	214	179	-49	-73
	σ_{22} (MPa)	147	192	206	261
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
90°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1082	1035	2026	1963
	σ_{22} (MPa)	106	141	107	138
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
45°	σ_{11} (MPa)	648	607	990	946
	σ_{22} (MPa)	127	166	157	200
	σ_{12} (MPa)	25	26	60	63

Premise: same σ_{22} values between the flat and curved situations

FLAT LAMINATE

Ansys

Analytical		Conv.	Conv.	0/90 UTP	0/90 UTP
		(O.P.)	(M.P.)	(O.P.)	(M.P.)
0°	σ_{11} (MPa)	760	936	482	673
	σ_{22} (MPa)	147	192	207	262
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
90°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1647	1808	2603	2744
	σ_{22} (MPa)	105	140	106	137
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
45°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1203	1372	1542	1707
	σ_{22} (MPa)	126	166	156	199
	σ_{12} (MPa)	26	27	62	64

FEM		Conv.	Conv.	0/90 UTP	0/90 UTP
		(O.P.)	(M.P.)	(O.P.)	(M.P.)
0°	σ_{11} (MPa)	766	941	484	673
	σ_{22} (MPa)	149	194	207	263
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
90°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1662	1825	2622	2763
	σ_{22} (MPa)	106	142	106	138
	σ_{12} (MPa)	0	0	0	0
45°	σ_{11} (MPa)	1213	1381	1552	1717
	σ_{22} (MPa)	128	168	158	201
	σ_{12} (MPa)	25	27	62	63

STAGE 2

Role of UTPs in quasi-isotropic laminates under LH2 tank conditions:

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AXIAL FORCES:

	Conv. Thickness (Original Prop.)	Conv. Thickness Modified Prop.	0/90 UTP (Original Prop.)	0/90 UTP Modified Prop.
F_x (N)	36425	43500	30300	35100
F_y (N)	53975	61050	47825	52625
K	1,48	1,40	1,58	1,50

K ratio dependence:

- [21%-30%] difference with the curved case.
- [5%-8%] decrease in the modified properties vs. the original properties case
- 7% increase in the UTPs vs. conventional thickness case

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CONCLUDING REMARKS

STAGE 1

Material behaviour at cryogenic temperatures:

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➤ **Material characterisation sheds light on the material ageing provoked by long-term cryogenic exposure, implying changes to the thermo-mechanical material properties**

$$E_{11} \downarrow, E_{22} \uparrow, \nu_{12} \downarrow, G_{12}, X_T \downarrow, Y_T \downarrow \downarrow, S \downarrow$$

$$\alpha_1 \downarrow \downarrow, \alpha_2 \uparrow \uparrow \uparrow$$

➤ **Important microstructural changes are happening on fibre and matrix after long-term cryogenic exposures to LN2**

STAGE 2

Role of UTPs in quasi-isotropic laminates under LH2 tank conditions:

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- Leakage testing of laminates after thermo-mechanical testing

➤ **Strategy to use UTPs on QI laminates is selected, looking for the minimum leakage as possible under service loads**

➤ **Determination of biaxial testing conditions of a flat QI CFRP laminate at RT that best reproduce the real conditions of a curved QI CFRP laminate in a LH2 tank**

The authors would also like to acknowledge Prof. Janis Varna and Prof. Bodo Fiedler for the enriching discussions on the subject

Funded by:

- Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities [PID2021-126279OB-I00]
- GERM from AICIA (Asociación de Investigación y Cooperación Industrial de Andalucía)

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THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

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